

A Study on the Application of the Film and television works about the law in Adult Legal Education

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Abstract:In the process of law popularization in China, law popularization educators have used various ways to popularize the law. The use of the rule of law in film and television productions to popularize the law has not been fully developed in a somewhat interesting way. The popularization of the rule of law in film and television works is in line with the cognitive laws of adults, after overcoming the lack of overall design, lack of training for teachers, copyright issues, it should be able to play a better role in the field of adult legal education.

Key words:Film and television works about the law, Adults, Legal education

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I. preamble

The dissemination of laws in our country has been carried out in a systematic and step-by-step manner, with governmental impetus, since the first five-year plan, which began in 1986. In all the working papers, the focus of the meeting was on how to educate the public about the law in an enjoyable way.

The use of film and television as a means of education has been promoted because of the visualization and impact of the visual, and a considerable number of studies have considered the rule of law film and television as a good

educational medium that combines artistic and legal seriousness. However, at present, there is no systematic study of the use of the rule of law in the work of adult law popularization, and there is a lack of systematic practice of the rule of law in the use of film and television works.

II.Theoretical Research and Practice on the Rule of Law in Film and Television

1. Types of legal-related film and television research in China

1.1 Take a film or television work as an example to illustrate certain legal issues

Such as Professor Zhu Su Li's "The Confusion of Qiu Ju and the Tragedy of Master Shankong" in "The Rule of Law and Its Local Resources" at the North University Law School; Mr. Su Li's monograph on "Qiu Ju's Lawsuit" became one of the most popular academic works in 1996.

1.2 A comprehensive study of legal cinema

One type of research paradigm is the value critique that began in the 1980s, using film and television works as a vehicle to analyze the values embodied in film and television works, study the legal culture and legal consciousness reflected in film and television works over the 40 years of reform and opening up, and analyze the changes in the

intentional dimension of the legal system in China during the 40 years of reform and opening up. Much of this research focuses on the use of film and television works as a lens through which to reflect changes in the rule of law in China.

1.3 Study of typified legal film and television works

Wigmore used to divide literature related to scope into four categories: depicting criminal pursuits and crimes, depicting court trials, depicting legal careers, and disseminating legal culture. The film and television works basically correspond to this.^[1]Such research focuses on the changes in the rule of law in society and changes in perceptions of rights as reflected in rule of law films and videos.

In fact, the current systematic study of how China uses the rule of law film and television to popularize the law publicity and education system research is relatively small, focusing on the film and television works as a carrier of diligent legal publicity and education research is not much. Data retrieval using the CNKI database was done and less research on methods of disseminating the law was found. Zhang Shibing's study of legal film and television in the process of building the rule of law, Gao Meng's study of the impact of legal film and television works on citizens' awareness of the rule of law are among the master's theses devoted to promoting the process of the rule of law through legal film and television works, and Shandong University's Zhang Beibei's study of rural topics in the new period, although they all involve how to combine film and television with legal education, but how to use the rule of law in film and television as a systematic and planned teaching method is still a gap.

In elite law school education, the use of classical rule of law film and television works as a medium for imparting knowledge has long been practiced. The use of film and television to influence the law can be said to

be a metamorphosis of the law and literature trend, Judge Benjamin Cardozo wrote in 1925 in the Yale Review on the literary style of sentencing opinions, and in 1907 the jurist John H. Wigmore published in the Illinois Law Review, No. 2, "Legal Fiction at a Glance," suggesting that jurists should understand human nature in the light of literary masterpieces. The jurisprudence of "law and literature" emerged in the United States in the 1970s. In the twentieth century, when art forms expressed in words are increasingly visualized, there has been a growing study of the relationship between film and law. It is the "seventh art" after literature, drama, painting, music, dance, and sculpture, integrating various arts to produce a new quality of "comprehensive art", which in turn leads to new research directions.

Systematic research on the use of the rule of law in film and television as a tool for the popularization of the law is rare, and research on the use and effectiveness of a form of instruction in the popularization of the law for adults is not fully developed. While there is considerable literature pointing to film and television works and their applicability to popular legal education, there is little elaboration and demonstration of the path to realization. "Teaching methods are the key and entry point for pedagogical reform. The development of information technology has revolutionized teaching methods. Many of the things that are dull and difficult to understand when taught in traditional ways can be presented intuitively and easily through multimedia technology, allowing people to learn and master in interesting and imaginative projects."^[2]

2. The practice of rule of law films and videos in rule of law education

2.1 Practice in law schools.

There are relevant elective courses in the law school, such as the rule of law film elective that Mr. Zhang Jianwei, who now works at Tsinghua University, has taken. Classics

such as "Morant the Horse Tamer" and "The Twelve Angry Men" were taught in the course. However, there are no systematic teaching materials or standardized curricula in this area, and such courses generally do not have designated teaching materials, relying mainly on the knowledge level of the lead teacher. Such elective courses are highly personal and require a high level of proficiency on the part of the instructor.

Among the main law school curriculum models currently in use, there are basically the following types.

(1) The rule of law film and television works appear as classroom instructional materials.

Because of the intuitive nature of film and television works, this method is mostly used when teaching a relatively obscure point of knowledge. Block clips of certain film and television productions can be interspersed in the classroom.

(2) The content of the rule of law in film and television works appears as an object of study.

An analysis of the legal issues involved in the work, as opposed to the previous situation in which only one point of knowledge was analysed, requires an understanding of the work as a whole and cannot be taken out of context. It generally requires learners to spend time watching film and television productions outside of class.

(3) Comparison of film and television productions from different French-speaking countries.

Comparing changes in the values of the same specific system under different legal systems (e.g. showing students the different environments in which lawyers practice in different legal systems, the way of thinking of different legal professional communities, and the state of belief in the law of people in different countries) Such invitations also require the

learner to spend some time outside the classroom to see the film or television work first, which is more time intensive.^[3]

2.2 Publicizing the practice of the media, radio, television, etc.

The popularization of the law is a method of publicity by using the popularized drama, drama series, etc., which is popular among the audience, and collecting materials extensively under the premise of full cooperation with the National Office for the Promotion of Law and other departments. Such an approach promotes justice and deters crime. But it must be pointed out that these plays are still quite a distance from the film and television works of art, generally in order to lay out the case and unfold the plot, the actor's role is basically a puppet for the clues to unfold, the effect is similar to a real person preaching knowledge. This form has the effect of popularizing the rule of law, but it is difficult to touch people on an emotional level, and lacks some emotional effects that really touch people's hearts and identify with the rule of law through emotional identification.

2.3 A brief screening in grass-roots legal literacy practice

In the publicity and promotion of the law held in street offices, neighborhood committees, institutions and enterprises, the screening of films on the rule of law as a mode of education and promotion of the law is also frequently used. However, these out-of-print subjects generally do not have dedicated law teachers, who are unable to interpret the film by extension, nor can they do in-depth theoretical analysis, most commonly people organize the viewer to watch the film and then end it without going further.

2.4 Less systematic use of the rule of law in adult legal literacy education

It should be said that, in the context of universal

education for adults on the rule of law, the form of video lessons is still rare and, where they are used, largely unsystematic. Although such electives are already available in major mainstream law schools, rule of law films are not part of the regular curriculum and there is no systematically developed teaching material. In addition to translating over of the American Paul. Bergman and Michael. Esmer's Justice in Images. At present, there are fewer books on the rule of law in film and television based on the reality in China, such as the aforementioned Li Yuqing's "The promotion of the rule of law in film and television works: 40 years of reform and opening up of film and television works as a perspective". This book is a meaningful work on the advancement of rule of law thinking in literature, the advancement of rule of law thinking in film and television works, the historical transformation of legal research discourse, and the development of rule of law third-party evaluation practices in China. But its creation was not originally intended to popularize and teach the law. It should be said that there is currently no system of relevant curricula and teaching materials.

III. Analysis of the applicability of the rule of law in adult legal literacy activities

1. The function of the rule of law in legal popularization activities

1.1 Popularizing knowledge and enhancing social awareness

The rule of law film and television works can be organized in a vivid image, and relatively obscure legal knowledge can be taught in a storytelling way, so as to increase legal knowledge as a whole.

1.2 Enhanced emotional identity

Emotional identity is a deep acceptance, not a suppressed obedience. The reading of legal texts can be an effective means of communication if the law is used only as a norm that needs to be enforced. Precisely because laws cannot be internalized into public rules if they are not accepted by the public, popularization of the law also requires an emotional and implicit influence.

2. Reasons for the systematic use of the rule of law in film and television productions and adult legal literacy activities

2.1 Lack of a complete curriculum or pedagogical design of rule of law films and videos that can be used as a model for general legal education

To study the history of the law popularization work in China, which started in 1986, the main body of law popularization education in China is various institutions, community streets, media, primary and secondary schools, community colleges, etc. Many of these main bodies of law popularization work do not have the ability to develop curriculum on their own, usually hiring teachers from professional colleges and universities, or by professionals with some legal practice experience (such as judges, prosecutors, lawyers) to give lectures. Community colleges with full-time faculty often also refer to the 16 main courses designated by the Ministry of Education's Steering Committee for the Teaching and Learning of Higher Education Law Subjects in Jurisprudence, Jurisprudence, Constitutional Law, History of Chinese Legal System, Criminal Law, Civil Law, Commercial Law, Intellectual Property Law, Economic Law, Criminal Procedure Law, Civil Procedure Law, Administrative Law and Administrative Procedure Law, International Law, Private International Law, International Economic Law, Environmental Law and Resource Protection Law, Labour Law and Social Security Law, and generally do not have the spare capacity to develop and design their own curriculum. In the existing system of

legal education, there is no curriculum or teaching design that can be directly applied to the work of legal education in general that is simply "fetishistic". While using of film and television works to demonstrate certain jurisprudence in the most emotionally convenient way, the absence of a stable and sufficiently authoritative instructional design is the primary problem.

2.2 Instability of teachers and the relative lack of intellectual and reading skills in the field of legal literacy

Among the main bodies of legal literacy education, such as units, community streets, media, primary and secondary schools and community colleges, there is usually a lack of sufficient capacity and a stable team of teachers to carry out commentary and film development on the rule of law. Community colleges are generally content to convey the basics, and full-time faculty are scarce and not at a level comparable to elite law schools that offer elective courses like the average law school faculty. Many ethics and rule of law teachers in primary and secondary schools lack a legal professional background, and unit publicity officers, etc., lack the ability to select appropriate film and television materials and make appropriate theoretical analysis.

2.3 Restrictions on equipment and premises

Forms of access to education, formal or informal, top-down indoctrination or environmental impact immersion. In many cases, the promotion of the rule of law is a one-off, transitional, such as the promotion of the rule of law in the square, display boards, etc., which brings about equipment and space limitations. The use of rule of law film and television for rule of law advocacy requires equipment to show the film and a place where teachers can be heard more quietly.

2.4 Film and television works face copyright problems, the way and place should be careful

Article 22 of the Copyright Law stipulates that published works may be translated or reproduced in small quantities for the purpose of classroom teaching or scientific research in schools for the use of teaching or scientific researchers, but may not be published or distributed. This is essentially a legally permitted use of a film or television work for educational purposes. The developed curriculum cannot be published without the purchase of a copyright, and thus cannot be used on a large scale, and thus cannot be mass-produced, and is difficult to commercialize - one of the reasons why the large-scale use of film and television works cannot be systematically promoted in mass legal education.

IV. How can the Rule of Law in Film and Television Be Used in Adult Legal Education

1. How to use the rule of law in popular legal education film and television works

1.1 Uniform purchase of relevant copyrights by law popular organizations

Once a published film or television work has been systematically used, edited and republished by the organization, the copyright of the work used must be properly handled. At present, the main body of popular legal education in China is relatively scattered, including communities, schools, universities, street offices, various units, etc., which usually do not have the funds and capacity to purchase copyright. Law schools with strong financial support are not the mainstay of popular legal education, perhaps some of the relevant government part with the agreement to buy the copyright of related film and television works would be a better choice.

1.2 Establishment of an updatable and systematic curriculum system

On the basis of copyright, the relevant governmental authorities or authoritative law schools may create a system of curricula, which should be flexible and in a block format that can be adapted over time and emerge as new works.

1.3 Special training for teachers

Taking the rule of law film and television works as the content of the popularization of the law, in fact, the level of the requirements for the teachers of the class is high. In addition, the level of teachers of the main body of legal literacy education is uneven, and it may be more effective to have special training to strengthen teachers. In view of the working hours of teachers in practice, teacher-specific reinforcement can be placed in the curriculum. At present, there are a variety of legal literacy education providers, and it is up to the competent authorities of authoritative institutions to remove the barriers between the providers, so that relatively qualified teachers (such as those in community colleges with a certain level of legal expertise) can provide guidance to other legal literacy practitioners and facilitate the movement of people and knowledge among them.

1.4 Film and television can make more use of new media platforms

With the development of new media platforms, the presentation of film and television is increasingly free from physical control. A variety of films, collections and in-depth tutorials are available in the form of web-based courses, either on the web or on mobile. The convergence of legal literacy with new media and new educational technologies is also a major trend that must be exploited.

2. The use of film and television works for adult legal literacy education should pay attention to the use of circumvention

Film and television works cannot be adopted directly

as teaching materials, but require in-depth analysis. Unspecified film and television productions are sometimes counterproductive rather than legal literacy.

2.1 Issues to be circumvented in the selection of material.

(1) Intellectual error.

If there is no distinction between formal and civil liability, it is even considered that the victim is exempt from criminal liability if he or she forgives.

(2) Knowledge obsolescence.

Sometimes it's because the response is chronological and should fit the historical flavor of the time, but is prone to misunderstanding.

Reflecting the social life of a particular era and documenting the changes in life is the source of cinematic art. Some of the unconventional behaviours of the police workers in such popular dramas as "The Defendant", "Never Close Your Eyes", "The Jade Goddess of Mercy" and "The Affair of a Snowy Moon" are in line with the social context of the time or are processed to highlight the contradictions of the case, and if not adequately explained, will easily cause misunderstandings to the viewer.

(3) Suspended, far from the actual situation

The working life of a thinking woman lawyer, for example, is told in 2004 in *The Good Lawyer*. The entire play is strung together by 22 cases. The lawyer's life is very exaggerated, which can be seen as a reference to the intention of the American legal drama, this drama reflects the lawyer's professional life and the relationship with the agent is very distorted, full of dogged bridges, the lawyer is dressed in exotic clothes, too suspended. Like many professional dramas, our country's current film and television productions

reflecting the legal profession have a general problem of suspension, which can be used as a counterpoint to the material.

2.2 Issues to be noted in the application of adult legal literacy works in adult legal literacy education

(1) The relationship between the artistry of film and television works and the accuracy of the law

As a work of art, film and television is more empirical and intuitive, embodying human aspirations for a better life and the pursuit of fairness, justice and goodness. At the same time, film and television works are intuitive, entertaining and artistic, which can evoke maximum emotional resonance. With the content of film and television works, people are often first to feel the direct knowledge and values that the works bring to the audience, and cannot calmly analyze the quasi-defective nature of the knowledge contained therein and whether the value judgment is correct. If there is wrong knowledge about the plot with a love story, it will have a more misleading effect. In some works, the mother of the murderer cries and begs the victim not to sue, and then the plot acknowledges that the victim's understanding can lead to the withdrawal of the prosecution case, which is extremely misleading to the viewer.

(2) The relationship between the formal flexibility of film and television law and the seriousness of popularizing knowledge - making it clear that this is still a form of teaching and not entertainment

Knowledge that is not expressed in a romanticized form is not serious, and the ultimate goal of using the rule of law in film and television productions to supplement the popularization of the law remains the popularization of legal knowledge and the firm belief in the rule of law rather than the entertainment of students. If the romanticized form deprives the law of its seriousness, this popularization of the

rule of law loses its meaning and even has negative effects. The rule of law in film and television is by its very nature a work of literature, not a simple account of reality, and the facts are sometimes embellished or simplified in order to highlight dramatic conflicts.

(3) The relationship between the popularity of selected materials and the educational nature of the content

The rule of law film and television works as part of film and television are also made up of individual film elements. A popular TV series often also includes a reworked background, a well-known director, a competent producer and an actor with the right appearance and acting skills. The selection of appropriate material by the legal practitioner cannot be based solely on the popularity of the material, some of which, while prominent in terms of popularity and entertainment, have less of a substantive educational function. There is another type of film that is made for the purpose of popularizing the law, which is often so didactic that it even becomes a drama about popularizing the law by mechanically displaying the legal provisions. The selection of material requires a balance of popularity among a large number of related rule of law films and television works, choosing the most appropriate. This also requires the capacity of teachers of law popularization.

V. In conclusion

Zhang Yaoxue, Director of the Higher Education Department of the Ministry of Education, has stated that "teaching methods are the key and entry point for teaching reform. The development of information technology has revolutionized teaching methods. Many of the things that are dull and difficult to understand when taught in traditional ways can be presented intuitively and easily through multimedia technology, allowing people to learn and master in interesting and imaginative projects." In particular, adult legal education needs to be guided by vivid and interesting

images.

Legal education for all should be accurately positioned as universal and generalized, serving the broadest masses and assisting the better realization of the socialist rule of law. The active development of teaching materials that meet the educational target requires more theoretical and practical innovations from educators of law popularization.

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